

ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF MARKETING IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the concept and essence of marketing, the role of marketing in the activities of the enterprise or firm, the organization of marketing activities in industrial enterprises, the conditions of marketing activities and marketing management in industrial enterprises, the most important components of the marketing complex .

Marketing is a key factor in coordinating the activities of the enterprise in the market, finding the owner of the product or service.

Marketing activity is the basis for a complex solution of its tasks: consumer search, identification of its capabilities, assessment of the level of competitiveness of the company and the product. Marketing activity involves a system of different activities that need to be analyzed and the best option selected.

At present, no enterprise in the system of market relations can operate normally in the enterprise without marketing services. And the usefulness of marketing is growing every moment. This is because people's needs are infinite and enterprise resources are limited. Each industry has its own needs, which are not always met in terms of quality. Each of them needs its own approach. Therefore, a company that can most accurately identify

and cover a variety of flavors in the new environment has a competitive advantage.

Modern marketing is considered as a system of organization of all activities of the enterprise for the production of goods, services and sales, a comprehensive study of the market and the provision of services based on real customer requirements, for maximum profit.

The goal of retailers' marketing activities is to manage their resources in the most efficient way, to achieve certain commercial results by meeting the needs of customers more effectively than competitors. The market is gradually saturated, achieving strategic goals is possible only on the basis of establishing long-term, trusting relationships with consumers and members of distribution networks.

The organization of marketing in the system of industrial enterprises is also a very important aspect and one of the

main factors of enterprise development. In the past, products were sold, but now they are being sold. The role of marketers in this is unique, they need to regularly collect information about periodic needs and requirements, the wishes and desires of consumers, and keep the head of the enterprise informed.

The organization of marketing in industrial enterprises includes:

- 1) Marketing planning system;
- 2) Marketing service organization system;
- 3) Marketing management system.

The marketing planning system includes marketing planning and strategic planning. Strategic planning involves several types of activities that determine the long-term plans of an enterprise or firm. In this case, each company plays an important role in the success of the enterprise, because each business is interconnected and ensures the continuity of each other. Even if one is left behind in the system, it affects the whole activity. Marketing planning is the process of developing individual plans for each individual product, product, or service. At the same time, it is understood that it has made a strategic decision to develop each of its areas. After that, a detailed marketing plan will be developed for them. Industrial enterprises mainly develop two types of plans - prospective and short-term. The long-term plan is developed for a period of 3-5 years and describes the characteristics of the main factors influencing the market of enterprise goods in the future, the goals and main strategic methods of obtaining the intended market share. The amount of expected profit, required expenses and

expected amount of income will be indicated.

Marketing Service Organization System - This system should ensure the marketing process, the implementation of this planning and the implementation of strategic plans. If the company is small, then only one marketer will be enough for the company and all the tasks will be assigned to him. In scientific language, we can call this employee sales manager, marketing manager, marketing director. When an enterprise is large, a team of marketers is formed and distributed under different responsibilities. These include sales people, sales managers, marketing researchers, advertising professionals, as well as those responsible for the production of various products, market segment functions are managed by the marketing department.

Marketing Management System - this system includes three types of control: control over the implementation of annual plans, control over profitability and control over the implementation of strategic goals. The task is to monitor the implementation of annual plans - to ensure that the company meets all the targets set in the annual plan. Profit control consists of the periodicity of actual profitability across different products, consumer groups, distribution channels, and order quantity. It is also important to learn how to determine the effectiveness of marketing, how to increase the effectiveness of various marketing activities. Monitoring the implementation of strategic goals includes a system for assessing the level of achievement of key objectives of marketing activities.

Marketing management plays an important and sometimes decisive role in the competition in the market. It is the product produced in the market and the labor expended on it that proves its social significance and is recognized by consumers. From this it can be noted that the topic of improving the marketing activities of the enterprise as a research topic for this final work is not only relevant, but also very promising.

Modern marketing is primarily aimed at adapting the supply of goods by enterprises to market requirements. The task of marketing is not only to focus on the sale of manufactured goods, but also to comprehensively study the needs and capabilities of consumers. These identified needs become the starting point for all decisions and actions to be taken in the enterprise. Such an understanding of marketing makes it a holistic concept of enterprise management as a whole, rather than an individual function of the enterprise carried out by the sales department.

Marketing tools, the purpose of which is to stimulate demand, are one of the most important components of the marketing mix. The main ones are: advertising, public relations, exhibitions, fairs, discounts, credit sales and more.

An advertisement is a message intended for a predetermined group of people, paid for by a particular customer, and aimed at motivating that group to specific actions that the customer wants. Before starting an advertising campaign, businesses need to decide what they want to achieve with advertising, which markets to conquer, how to shape the message, what advertising tools to use, when and

how often to advertise, and how much to spend on it. Thus, advertising affects everyone's interests at any day of their lives and is accepted by us as part of everyday mass culture.

Public relations is defined as "promoting a common understanding of goodwill between an individual, organization and other people, groups of people, or society as a whole through the dissemination of explanatory materials, the development of exchanges, and the assessment of public reaction". "The PR manager's job is to prepare and hold press conferences, briefings, press cocktails, presentations, meetings with company executives, press releases, photos and other materials for publication, on the basis of which articles, essays and reports are written.

A good way to present the company to a wide audience, as well as to establish new useful contacts and preserve old ones, is to participate in these exhibitions and industry conferences. Careful preparation should be made to participate in activities so that the funds spent for these purposes are not wasted.

Thus, with the help of advertising and PR, a specific connection is established with existing or potential buyers, the purpose of which is to create a positive idea about the goods and services offered and to form the image of the company.

As F. Kotler describes, marketing management is the analysis, planning, implementation, and monitoring of activities aimed at establishing, strengthening, and supporting beneficial exchanges with target customers to achieve specific organizational goals. for example, making a profit, increasing sales, increasing

market share, and so on. The task of marketing management is to influence the level, timing, and nature of demand in a way that helps the organization achieve its goals. Simply put, marketing management is demand management. There are five main forms (concepts) in which commercial organizations carry out marketing activities:

- the concept of production improvement;
- the concept of product improvement;

- the concept of strengthening commercial activity;
- marketing concept;
- the concept of social and ethical marketing.

The use of each of them is mandatory, first and foremost, and raises the question of how the balance of interests of producers, consumers, and society as a whole should be. After all, often these interests contradict each other.

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